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Overview of writing systems and character encoding standards and article formats used in the domain

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1 Introduction

Writing systems are the visual representations of language. Lexical resources have to represent the entire lexical system of a language digitally, at least potentially. As a consequence, lexical resources may have to handle the entirety of a writing system used to represent a given language and represent this information in a standardized digital manner. The information to every lexeme of a language has to be represented by one (or more) lexical entries, which again needs to be coherently represented digitally.

There may exist close to three hundred known writing systems in current and historical use.¹ These writing systems differ in appearance and inventory, but more crucially in their structure and organizing principles. Technically, writing systems are represented in digital technical systems through various character encodings. These character encodings differ in scope and technical implementation. Computer fonts are then used to render the encoded character in a specific typeface or font. Again there are different formats for computer fonts which differ in their capability of representing characteristics of different writing systems.

Besides character encodings for representing different writing systems and computer fonts for rendering the encoded characters, article formats for lexicographical entries constitute a third important component of all digital lexical resources. These article formats are used to structure and organize the information contained in a lexical entry. They are used to represent the information in a standardized and coherent manner.

This document provides an overview of writing systems, recommended character encodings, and standardized article formats used in the domain of lexical resources. It discusses the importance of these components for the representation and processing of language data and provides examples of how they are used in practice.

2 Terminology

For this document we will use the terms *grapheme* and *allograph*, *glyphs*, *characters*, as well as *code points*.

- A **grapheme** can be understood as the smallest identifiable unit of a writing system which differentiates meaning (Coulmas 1999, p. 175). Graphemes are conventionally represented between angle brackets ⟨ ⟩.
- **Allographs** are realized variants of a grapheme (Coulmas 1999, p. 9). Allographs are also represented between angle brackets ⟨ ⟩. Latin alphabet short or terminal s ⟨s⟩ and the long s ⟨ſ⟩ can be understood as contextually determined allographs. Similarly, initial, medial and final letter forms in Arabic – such as initial ⟨ﻡ⟩, medial ⟨ﻡَ⟩, and final ⟨ﻡِ⟩ of the Arabic letter ⟨ﻡ⟩ mīm – can be understood as contextual allographs.
- When describing encoding systems, the term **character** is understood as the abstract representation of the smallest components of written language that have semantic value (Unicode 15.0, p. 15). Characters in encoding systems are the equivalent of graphemes in the structural linguistic study of writing systems. However, some, especially non-printing, characters – such as U+0020 SPACE, U+00A0 NO-BREAK SPACE, U+180E MONGOLIAN VOWEL SEPARATOR or U+200C ZERO WIDTH NON-JOINER – would be generally not considered graphemes.

¹ <https://www.worldswritingsystems.org/faq.html>

- A **glyph** is the visual representation of a grapheme and can be understood as the concrete realization of a character in a specific typeface or font (Unicode 15.0, p. 15). It is thus similar, though not identical, to the concept of an allograph. Glyphs are often represented between in quotation marks, e.g. “a”, “a”, or “a”.
- Technically, characters are represented by **code points** that reside only in a memory representation (Unicode 15.0, p. 15). Unicode code points are generally represented as four-digit hexadecimal numbers prefixed with U+. Thus, the codepoint for the character corresponding to the Latin alphabet grapheme ⟨a⟩ is given as U+0061. Characters are represented by the code point followed by the Unicode name of the character in capital letters or small caps, resulting in the sequence U+0061 LATIN SMALL LETTER A.

grapheme	⟨a⟩	⟨अ⟩
character	U+0061 LATIN SMALL LETTER A	U+0905 DEVANAGARI LETTER A
code point	U+0061	U+0905
glyph	“a”	“अ”

In this text, we will take the convention to accompany every reference to a Unicode character with a glyph in quotation marks resulting in a sequence like this: “a” U+0061 LATIN SMALL LETTER A or “अ” U+0905 DEVANAGARI LETTER A.

3 Writing systems

Writing systems constitute a vast area of study and research. The study of writing systems is called graphemics (Coulmas 1999, p. 176) or grapholinguistics (Meletis and Dürscheid 2022). Given the breadth of the topic, this document can only provide a brief overview of the variety of writing systems. For a comprehensive introduction to the study of writing systems see Coulmas (2002).

As mentioned in the introduction, there may be up to 300 writing systems in current and historical use. At the very least, the 161 writing systems supported by Unicode² give a lower limit of known writing systems. These writing systems differ in appearance and inventory, but more crucially in their structure and organizing principles. Writing systems can be classified according to various criteria. A common typology is based on the relationship between the dominant organizational unit of a writing system to linguistic units. Writing systems can be classified as alphabets, abjads, abugidas, syllabaries, and logosyllabaries.

3.1 Alphabetic writing systems

Alphabetic writing systems come in three subtypes: alphabets, abjads, abugidas. They all take the phoneme as the basic linguistic structuring level and relate their graphemes and the minimal units of speech, the phonemes (cf. Coulmas 1999, p. 9). Alphabets have each grapheme stand for a consonant or vowel (Daniels 2017, p. 76). Everyone reading this document is familiar with at least one alphabet, the Latin alphabet. The Latin alphabet (ISO 15924 **Latn**) is also the most widely used alphabet. It is used with smaller variation to write languages, as diverse as English, Turkish, Hungarian, Kalaallisut, Hausa, Khasi, Guaraní, or Tetum. Other alphabets include the Cyrillic alphabet (кирилица, ISO 15924 **Cyrl**), the Greek alphabet (ελληνικό αλφάβητο, ISO 15924 **Grek**), the Georgian alphabet (დაბნერლობა, ISO 15924 **Geor**), as well as obsolete systems like the Runic

² <https://www.unicode.org/standard/supported.html>

Canada. Despite its name, it is not as clearly a syllabary as the name might suggest but has structural characteristic of an abugida. Like syllabaries and abugidas, Canadian Aboriginal syllabics has the syllable as the basic unit of representation, but similar to abugidas it takes the segments onset consonants, vowels and coda consonants as separately represented units, although rotating the grapheme as the mechanism to indicate the vowel quality is unusual for a writing system (Nichols 1996). As most other abugidas, Canadian Aboriginal syllabics is written from left to right.

3.2 Syllabaries

Syllabaries are writing systems where a grapheme has a syllable as its basic unit (Coulmas 1999, p. 483) or moras (Daniels 2017, p. 82). The most widely used syllabaries are the two Japanese Kana Hiragana (ひらがな, ISO 15924 **Hira**) and Katakana (カタカナ, ISO 15924 **Kana**). Other syllabaries include the Cherokee script (ᎠᎿᎺ, ISO 15924 **Cher**, Daniels 2017, p. 76), the Vai script (𞤀𞤁, ISO 15924 **Vai**, Daniels 2017, p. 77), the Yi script (ꨀꨁꨂ, ISO 15924 **Yiii**, Coulmas 1999, p. 568), and the ancient Linear B script (ISO 15924 **Linb**, Coulmas 1999, p. 297). The Linear B is a syllabary, but it also has some logographic elements, called pictorial signs by Coulmas (1999, p. 298). The Japanese syllabaries historically developed from Chinese logographic graphemes.

3.3 Logographies

Logographies, called morphosyllabic script by Daniels (2017, p. 81), are writing systems where a grapheme stands for a morpheme or a word. The only remaining logographic system in modern use is the Chinese script (汉字/漢字, ISO 15924 **Hani**). The Chinese script is used to write Standard Chinese (so called Mandarin), Yue (including Cantonese), Wu, Min, Hakka, and other Chinese languages. In Japanese, Chinese characters (Kanji 漢字) are used in combination with the Kana syllabaries. In Korean, Chinese characters (Hanja 漢字) are used in combination with the Korean alphabet Hangeul (한글, ISO 15924 **Hang**). The Korean script consisting of Hanja and Hangeul together is registered as ISO 15924 **Kore**. There are 54,678 Chinese graphemes (Yin 2016, p. 57), while the Unicode Standard includes nearly 100,000 CJK unified characters (Unicode 15.0, p. 760).

Other logographies include the Egyptian hieroglyphs (ISO 15924 **Egyp**), the Mayan script (ISO 15924 **Maya**), and the Cuneiform script (ISO 15924 **Xsux**). Logographies, ancient and current, have by their very nature a large inventory of graphemes. There is also a tendency to use logographies in multilingual contexts, as the Chinese script is used to write several languages, and the same was true for cuneiform in the ancient Near East (Coulmas 1999, p. 102). This is possible, because the graphemes do not directly reference the phonemic structure of a morpheme, but the morpheme itself. This allows for a more direct representation of the meaning of a word, which is especially useful in a multilingual context. However, many logographic systems use the rebus principle as a strategy to increase the expressive power of logographic systems (Coulmas 1999, p. 433).

4 Character encodings

To represent different writing systems digitally, character encoding systems are used. Character encoding systems define how graphemes and other characters are represented in digital form independent from their appearance. Character encoding standards provide a consistent method for representing text data in binary formats, regardless of the platform or operating system. By using standardized character encoding systems, data can be reliably exchanged and interpreted between different systems, which improves interoperability, data exchange, and sustainability.

Historically, there were numerous character writing system as well as platform or operating system vendor specific encoding systems. Some were standardized, such as ASCII or JIS X 0208, while others were vendor specific, such as the Sharp MZ character sets,⁴ or software specific, such as TeX's OT1 encoding (Knuth 1984). While there are numerous historical character encoding systems and standards, *The Unicode Standard* (current version Unicode 15.1) is the most comprehensive and widely used character encoding standard, today. Unicode is an international standard that aims to provide a unique code point for every character in every known writing system. We unequivocally recommend the use of Unicode for all digital lexical resources. Unicode provides several encoding schemes, including UTF-8, UTF-16, and UTF-32, which allow for the representation of characters in different manners depending on the current requirements. UTF-8 is the most commonly used encoding scheme and we recommend it generally, but at least for data storage as well as for web publishing. UTF-8 is also compatible with ASCII, which makes it a good choice for backward compatibility with older systems. In case you are working with a writing system that is – as of now – not included in the Unicode standard, the best way to proceed is discussed under *Working with writing Systems not included in Unicode* below.

Of all the various encoding standard prior to Unicode, ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) is the most important and most widely used standard. ASCII was originally a 7-bit code and had just 128 code points, of which only 95 were printable characters. It was later extended to the 8-bit ISO/IEC-8859-1 standard, which retained the original printable ASCII characters and added additional characters for European languages. Unicode (encoded as UTF-8) is compatible with ASCII and ISO/IEC-8859-1.

Glyph	ASCII	ISO/IEC-8859-1	Unicode
TAB	0x09	–	U+0009
SPACE	0x20	0x20	U+0020
!	0x21	0x21	U+0021
5	0x35	0x35	U+0035
A	0x41	0x41	U+0041
a	0x61	0x61	U+0061
©	–	0xA9	U+00A9
æ	–	0xE6	U+00E6

The ISO/IEC-8859 family of standards did cover other variants of the Latin alphabet, such as ISO/IEC-8859-2 for Central and Eastern European languages and ISO/IEC-8859-10 for Nordic languages. While ISO/IEC-8859-5 covered Latin and Cyrillic scripts and ISO/IEC-8859-6 covered Latin and Arabic scripts.

5 Unicode

Since 1991 (Unicode 1.0.0), the Unicode Consortium maintains and develops The Unicode Standard (current version Unicode 15.1), generally referred to simply as Unicode. Unicode covers currently 161 writing systems with code points for all (or nearly all) their graphemes and additional code points for non-printing characters such as control codes and layout controls.

As already covered in the section on Terminology, Unicode distinguishes between characters, code points, and glyphs. Characters are the abstract representation of the smallest components of written language that have semantic value. Code points are the numerical values that represent characters in the Unicode standard. Glyphs are the visual representations of characters in a specific typeface or font. Code points can be encoded through different encoding schemes: UTF-8, UTF-16, and UTF-

⁴ Personal Computer MZ-700 Owner's Manual. Sharp Corporation. 1983. p. 154–156.

32. UTF-8 is the most commonly used and is backwards compatible with ASCII, while UTF-16 and UTF-32 are not.

Glyph	Character name	Code point	Block	UTF-8 (hex)	UTF-16 (hex)
&	AMPERSAND	U+0026	Basic Latin	0x26	0x0026
A	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A	U+0041	Basic Latin	0x41	0x0041
ä	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH DIAERESIS	U+00E4	Latin-1 Supplement	0xC3 0xA4	0x00E4
щ	CYRILLIC SMALL LETTER SHCHA	U+0449	Cyrillic	0xD1 0x89	0x0449
漢	CJK UNIFIED IDEOGRAPH-6F22	U+6F22	CJK Unified Ideographs	0xE6 0xBC 0xA2	0x6F22
€	EURO SIGN	U+20AC	Currency Symbols	0xE2 0x82 0xAC	0x20AC
😊	GRINNING FACE	U+1F600	Emoticons	0xF0 0x9F 0x98 0x80	0xD83D 0xDE00
	CJK Unified Ideograph-30EDD	U+30EDD	CJK Unified Ideographs Extension G	0xF0 0xB0 0xBB 0x9D	0xD883 0xDEDD

5.1 Unicode blocks

Code points are grouped in Unicode blocks. Blocks are non-overlapping named ranges of multiple of 16 code points. Writing systems can be spread over several non-adjacent blocks and blocks can contain characters used by more than one writing system (Unicode 15.0, p. 44). Besides assigned characters, blocks can contain reserved code points. Block names are in English and contain only ASCII characters. In this document, the names are accompanied by code point ranges in parentheses, e.g. *Alchemical Symbols* (U+1F700–U+1F77F) or *Tai Tham* (U+1A20–U+1AAF). Unicode 15.1 defines 328 blocks, of which the two largest are special areas for private use Supplementary Private Use Area-A (U+F0000–U+FFFFD) and Supplementary Private Use Area-B (U+100000..U+10FFFFD) encompass 65,534 code points each. These two ranges will remain unassigned by the Unicode Consortium and can be used by individuals or organizations through private agreement among cooperating users. The largest proper range is CJK Unified Ideographs Extension B (U+20000–U+2A6DF) encompassing 42,720 code points with 42,720 assigned characters. The smallest blocks cover the minimal 16 code points, of these the block Specials (U+FFFF0–U+FFFFF) with only 6 assigned characters is the smallest.

New scripts are added to the Unicode standard as blocks. The latest addition to the standard were the blocks Kawi (U+11F00–U+11F5F) and Nag Mundari (1E4D0–1E4FF) in 2022 (Unicode 15.0). The Unicode Consortium has a defined process for adding new scripts to the standard, which includes a proposal and review process.⁵ The Unicode Consortium maintains a pipeline document for characters currently in the approval process⁶ and it also maintains a roadmap document of scripts that are currently not encoded in Unicode, but for which proposals have been submitted and are under consideration.⁷

⁵ <https://www.unicode.org/pending/proposals.html>

⁶ <https://www.unicode.org/alloc/Pipeline.html>

⁷ <https://www.unicode.org/roadmaps/index.html>

5.2 Combining characters

Unicode contains a type of character that is called combining character and is defined by the standard as a mark of some kind intended to be positioned relative to some other character, which is referred to as its associated base character (Unicode 15.0, p. 54). Combining characters are usually depicted with an associated dotted circle (itself a character: U+25CC ◌ DOTTED CIRCLE), which represents the base character.

While in the Unicode encoding, the combining character follows the base character. The glyph for the combining character may appear above, below, to either side, crossing through, or even surrounding the glyph of the base character. For example, the sequence of the glyph “a” U+0061 LATIN SMALL LETTER A and “◌” U+0308 COMBINING DIAERESIS results in the complex glyph ä (a + ◌ → ä).

Some writing systems, in particular abudigas rely heavily on combining characters to render consonant vowel combinations. For example, the Tamil word இட்லி itli contains the independent “இ” U+0B87 TAMIL LETTER I and the combining “ி” U+0BBF TAMIL VOWEL SIGN I. Both representing the same phoneme /i/. The comparable Devanagari sequence “ल” U+0932 DEVANAGARI LETTER LA and “ि” U+0940 DEVANAGARI VOWEL SIGN II results in the complex glyph लि (ल + ि → लि), with the combining vowel sign being rendered in front of the consonant glyph.

5.3 Conjuncts

South Asian abudigas such as Devanagari or Bengali, also use conjuncts, which are complex glyphs that represent a sequence of two or more consonants. For example, the Sanskrit word धार्ष्यं dhārṣṭya contains the ligature <र्ष्य> rṣṭya consisting of four consonant graphemes – <र>, <ष>, <ट>, and <य> – and an inherent vowel /a/.

धार्ष्यं Dhārṣṭya am, n. violence, boldness, daringness, audacity, arrogance, impudence, rudeness.

The ligature <र्ष्य> rṣṭya is technically the conjunct of seven characters:

1. “र” U+0930 DEVANAGARI LETTER RA
2. “◌्” U+094D DEVANAGARI SIGN VIRAMA
3. “ष” U+0937 DEVANAGARI LETTER SSA
4. “◌्” U+094D DEVANAGARI SIGN VIRAMA
5. “ट” U+091F DEVANAGARI LETTER TTA
6. “◌्” U+094D DEVANAGARI SIGN VIRAMA
7. “य” U+092F DEVANAGARI LETTER YA

and can be constructed step by step as follows:

1. र + ष → र्ष
2. र्ष + ट → र्षट
3. र्षट + य → र्ष्य

Conjuncts are intended to be rendered by ligatures, thus the sequence “क” U+0915 DEVANAGARI LETTER KA, “◌्” U+094D DEVANAGARI SIGN VIRAMA, and “ष” U+0937 DEVANAGARI LETTER SSA should always be rendered as the ligature “क्ष”, itself not a character in Unicode. To prevent the rendering of conjuncts as ligatures, the Unicode standard provides the zero-width non-joiner (ZWNJ) U+200C ZERO WIDTH NON-JOINER. The ZWNJ is inserted between the two consonants, but following the virāma, to prevent the rendering of conjuncts as ligatures, thus the sequence “क

U+0915 DEVANAGARI LETTER KA, “॰” U+094D DEVANAGARI SIGN VIRAMA, U+200C ZERO WIDTH NON-JOINER, and “ॲ” U+0937 DEVANAGARI LETTER SSA should be rendered as the sequence “कॲ” (क + ॰ + ZWNJ + ॲ).

5.4 Normalization

Unicode allows for multiple ways to represent a complex character. For example, ä can be represented as the sequence of the character “a” U+0061 LATIN SMALL LETTER A and “◌̈” U+0308 COMBINING DIAERESIS or as the composite “ä” U+00E4 LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH DIAERESIS. The Unicode Standard defines a set of normalization algorithms to enable standardized decomposition and character ordering.⁸ The Normalization Form C (NFC) erases any canonical differences, and generally produces a composed result. For example, the sequence “a” U+0061 LATIN SMALL LETTER A and “◌̈” U+0308 COMBINING DIAERESIS is converted to “ä” U+00E4 LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH DIAERESIS in this form.⁹ The Normalization Form D (NFD) erases any canonical differences, and produces a decomposed result. For example, “ä” U+00E4 LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH DIAERESIS is converted to “a” U+0061 LATIN SMALL LETTER A and “◌̈” U+0308 COMBINING DIAERESIS in this form. This form is most often used in internal processing, such as in collation.¹⁰

To order characters in decomposed results, combining characters are assigned a canonical combining class value. The combining class values are used by ordering algorithms to determine if two sequences of combining marks should be considered canonically equivalent. The canonical combining class value is a number between 0 and 255 that is assigned to each combining character. Non-combining characters are assigned a 0.¹¹

The decomposable character “ê” U+1EBF LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH CIRCUMFLEX AND ACUTE is used in Vietnamese orthography. It is defined as equivalent to “ê” U+00EA LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH CIRCUMFLEX and “◌̈́” U+0301 COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT. The character “ê” U+00EA is itself defined as “e” U+0065 LATIN SMALL LETTER E and “◌̂” U+0302 COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT. The canonical decomposition of “ê” is thus “e” U+0065 LATIN SMALL LETTER E, “◌̂” U+0302 COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT, and “◌̈́” U+0301 COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT. The combining classes for the two accents are both 230, thus “ê” is not equivalent to “e” U+0065 LATIN SMALL LETTER E, “◌̂” U+0302 COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT, and “◌̈́” U+0301 COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT.

Normalization is important for collation, searching, and comparison of text data. It is also important for text processing, as it ensures that text data is represented in a consistent and standardized form. Normalization is best performed using Unicode libraries and tools.

5.5 Writing direction and bidirectional text

Writing systems have different conventions for arranging characters into lines. Such conventions are referred to as a script’s directionality. So, Latin script (ISO 15924 **Latn**) is an example of a left-to-right writing systems and Arabic script (ISO 15924 **Arab**) is an example of a right-to-left writing system. In both types of writing systems, the lines are arranged from top to bottom. Chinese script (ISO 15924 **Hani**) is an example of a writing system that is nowadays written mostly left-to-right but

⁸ <https://www.unicode.org/reports/tr15/>

⁹ https://www.unicode.org/glossary/#normalization_form_c

¹⁰ https://www.unicode.org/glossary/#normalization_form_d

¹¹ https://www.unicode.org/reports/tr44/#Canonical_Combining_Class_Values

used to be written top-to-bottom with lines then arranged from right to left. Chinese characters remain the same, regardless of the directionality of a text, but punctuation marks change according writing directionality. Mongolian (ISO 15924 **Mong**) is usually written top-to-bottom, with lines arranged from left to right. When Mongolian is written horizontally, the characters are rotated.

Historically, there was more variation in writing directionality, not only among different scripts, but also within the same script. For example, the ancient Greek script (ISO 15924 **Gre**) could be written from right to left, left to right, and boustrophedon (alternating right-to-left and left-to-right). In Unicode, the directionality of a script is defined by the standard and is used to determine the default direction of text in that script. The Unicode Standard provides mechanisms to handle the display of text that contains both left-to-right and right-to-left scripts, also called bidirectional text, or *bidi* for short. In lexicography, bidirectionality may occur in bilingual dictionaries, etymological information as well as when phonetic information is added to an otherwise right-to-left context.

Unicode provides robust support for bidirectional text. In particular, Unicode provides a bidirectional algorithm to handle the management of text that contains both left-to-right and right-to-left scripts. The framework for managing bidirectionality is described in Goregaokar and Leroy (2023). The remaining text is heavily based on this report. The algorithm determines the direction of each character based on its Unicode character properties and the context in which it appears. Each character in Unicode is assigned an implicit bidirectional type. The bidirectional types left-to-right and right-to-left are strong types, and characters of those types are called strong directional characters. Numbers are weak types and are called weak directional characters. All other characters are called neutral, except for characters belonging to the explicit directional formatting characters. The algorithm uses the implicit bidirectional types of the characters in a text to arrive at a reasonable display ordering for text. The explicit directional formatting characters can be used to manage and change the outcome of the algorithm. This can be particularly important in typographically dense contexts such as lexicographical entries. The directional formatting characters are part of the block General Punctuation (U+2000–U+206F) and consist of 12 characters, categorized into three types: embedding, override, and isolate.

Label	Code Point	Name
LRE	U+202A	LEFT-TO-RIGHT EMBEDDING
RLE	U+202B	RIGHT-TO-LEFT EMBEDDING

LRE marks that the following text should be treated embedded left-to-right, for example an English phrase in Latin script in an otherwise Arabic text. Conversely RLE Treat the following text as embedded right-to-left.

Label	Code Point	Name
LRO	U+202D	LEFT-TO-RIGHT OVERRIDE
RLO	U+202E	RIGHT-TO-LEFT OVERRIDE

Similarly, LRO and RLO force the following characters to be treated as strong left-to-right or right-to-left characters, respectively. The override can be used to force an alphanumerical sequence (Latin characters and Western Arabic numerals) in an otherwise right-to-left context to be treated as an right-to-left sequence. However, Goregaokar and Leroy (2023) state that overrides are to be avoided wherever possible, because of security concern.

Label	Code Point	Name
PDF	U+202C	POP DIRECTIONAL FORMATTING

PDF terminates the scope of the last LRE, RLE, LRO, or RLO whose scope has not yet been terminated.

The explicit directional formatting characters of the typw isolate can be used to signal to the algorithm that a segment of text is to be treated as directionally isolated from its surroundings. Isolate type characters are similar to embedding characters, but they have the effect of a neutral character on the ordering of the surrounding text, while an embedding roughly has the effect of a strong character. The text inside the isolate has no effect on the ordering of the text outside it.

Label	Code Point	Name
LRI	U+2066	LEFT-TO-RIGHT ISOLATE
RLI	U+2067	RIGHT-TO-LEFT ISOLATE
FSI	U+2068	FIRST STRONG ISOLATE
PDI	U+2069	POP DIRECTIONAL ISOLATE

LRI and RLI tell the algorithm to treat the following text as isolated and left-to-right or right-to-left, respectively. FSI tells the algorithm to treat the following text as isolated and in the direction of its first strong directional character that is not inside a nested isolate. PDI ends the scope of the last LRI, RLI, or FSI.

The implicit directional marks act exactly like right-to-left or left-to-right characters, just that they are non-printing and have no semantic content beyond their implicit directionality. They have a very local effect and are a light-weight alternative to explicit embeddings or overrides.

Label	Code Point	Name
LRM	U+200E	LEFT-TO-RIGHT MARK
RLM	U+200F	RIGHT-TO-LEFT MARK
ALM	U+061C	ARABIC LETTER MARK

For example, the RLM character can be used to correct the placement of punctuation relating to a right-to-left text **لا!** in a left-to-right context. With RLM U+200F RIGHT-TO-LEFT MARK following the exclamation mark, the exclamation mark, itself a neutral character, is in local right-to-left context **!لا** and will be rendered appropriately in relation to the Arabic exclamation.

In a web context most of the management of bidirectionality should be handled by HTML and CSS mechanisms and the browser.

The Unicode Standard does not provide similarly strong mechanisms to handle the interaction between top-to-bottom and left-to-right or right-to-left text. It does not provide explicit control characters for top-to-bottom text.

5.6 Unicode rendering

Character encoding systems are an crucial part of working with the world's writing systems and Unicode is the most comprehensive and widely used character encoding standard, today. However, there is a whole stack of digital resources like fonts and software (libraries) that are needed to render Unicode encoded information for screen or print. The stack consists of fonts, font rasterizers, bidirectional engines, text shaping engines, layout engines. These components need to work together to allow for the correct rendering of text in different writing systems. For example, the handling of Devanagari clusters was different between Unicode and OpenType, leading to inconsistent results.¹²

¹² <https://www.unicode.org/L2/L2021/21112-deva-cluster-valid.pdf>

The discussion of the complete stack and its technical and practical implication goes far beyond the scope of this document. When working with complex, newly encoded or otherwise marginal writing systems, it is important to keep in mind, that Unicode encoded information must pass through a large stack of complex software to become beautifully rendered glyphs for the researcher of end user and problems or inconsistencies can arise at any point.

For the end user, most aspects of the stack are hidden inside complex applications, such as Web browsers or word processing software, so that the differences between various implementation of parts of the required stack, are irrelevant for the creator of an lexical resource. It remains important to make sure that the whole rendering of the resource works for as many users as possible. The only part where one can select and prescribe an individual component are fonts. Operation systems come with a collection of fonts that provide a decent coverage of many Unicode blocks and Web browsers come with the capability to render Web fonts provided by the resource. Fonts with a wide coverage of Unicode blocks are available from several sources, including:

- Junicode¹³
- Google Noto¹⁴ large family of typefaces
- SIL-Fonts¹⁵ open license fonts for several writing systems

5.7 Working with writing systems not included in Unicode

Given the wide range of writing systems supported by Unicode, it is rare to encounter a writing system that is not yet covered by the standard or that is not yet in the roadmap. However, if you are working on such a language it is crucial to work with an internal transparent encoding, for example using the mechanisms provided by the the private use area of Unicode or better in most cases to work with a frame work the research team is familiar with such as TEI. TEI provides a comprehensive framework for the encoding of text in any writing system and is widely used in the text-based digital humanities. Iglesia et al. (2021) is a recent example of a project using TEI to encode a writing system not yet included in Unicode. If the writing system of the language you are working with is fully understood but not supported by Unicode, you may also use an established transliteration system to represent the text in a different or again develop a new transliteration system and document it.

However you choose to proceed. It is important to document your work, publish the documentation, and publish about how and why you did things the way you did. This will later help you or other to convert your work into a Unicode compliant format, once the writing system is included in the standard. In parallel, you should also contact the Unicode Consortium and evaluate the possibility of submitting a proposal for the inclusion of the writing system in the standard.

6 Transliteration standards

Transliteration is the process of rendering one writing system in terms of another. In contrast to transcriptions that target phonetic and/or phonological properties of the object language, transliterations target the graphemic level of a written resource and render it in a different writing system. The transliteration systems we have encounter are Latin alphabet-based systems and we will restrict our discussion to those.

¹³ <https://psb1558.github.io/Junicode-font/>

¹⁴ <https://fonts.google.com/noto>

¹⁵ <https://software.sil.org/fonts/>

There might be a set of established transliteration conventions and standards for a given writing system, as is the case for Arabic (e.g. Brockelmann et al. 1935) or Sanskrit (Scharf and Hyman 2011). In these cases, it might not be important which transliteration system you select, as long as they are equally appropriate or even isomorph. For the end user it might be important to provide a conversion between different transliterations. If the systems are incompatible, make sure to select the most adequate for your purpose. If you work with an understudied language with a rare or language specific writing system you might have to develop your own transliteration system. In such cases, it is important to make yourself familiar with transliteration systems for related writing systems, follow established best practices, document your transliteration system, and make it available to others.

The fact that lexical resources often aim for a comprehensive coverage of a language can also lead to situations where a transliteration system is not comprehensive enough to cover all edge cases of graphemes of a writing system, see for example Rau (2017) for a discussion of such a case in Sanskrit. In such cases, it is important to document the limitations of the transliteration system and choose a way to retain the information from the original writing system in your representation.

In the case of logographic writing systems, proper transliteration is often not practical and a system of romanization is used to represent the pronunciation of words or characters in a different writing system. For example, the Chinese script can be romanized into the Latin alphabet using the Pinyin system, which represents the pronunciation of Chinese characters using Roman letters. Transliteration systems for logographic writing systems are often not proper transliterations and highly lossy, but they might be still useful for representing the pronunciation of words in a different writing system in a conventional and standardized way.

7 Article formats in lexical resources

7.1 Types of lexical resources

Lexical resources are diverse collections of linguistic data used to support various language-related tasks. Common types of lexical resources include dictionaries, thesauri, corpora, and lexical databases. Dictionaries are structured collections of words, typically accompanied by definitions, translations, and other linguistic information. They serve as reference tools for the meaning, pronunciation, and usage of words in a particular language or across different languages. Thesauri, on the other hand, provide synonyms and associative relationships between words, helping to expand vocabulary and improve expression in a language. Corpora are extensive collections of texts or linguistic data that can be used for linguistic analysis, machine learning, and other language technology applications. They provide insights into language usage in various contexts, enabling the identification of linguistic patterns and properties.

Dictionaries are usually organized (alphabetically) and contain entries for individual words or terms. Each entry may include various information, such as the definition of the word, its pronunciation, grammatical information like part of speech, usage examples, and translations into other languages.

Thesauri are also organized in entries but offer synonyms and associative relationships between words. A thesaurus can provide alternative words for a given concept or idea, helping to expand vocabulary and improve expression in a language.

Corpora consist of extensive collections of texts or linguistic data, often organized thematically or by genre. Each corpus can contain hundreds or even thousands of text documents written in a specific language or on a specific topic. The texts in a corpus can be in raw form or linguistically annotated, with additional metadata such as author names, publication dates, and genre

information. By structuring texts in a corpus, linguists and researchers can analyze linguistic patterns, develop statistical models, and study linguistic phenomena to gain insights into language usage.

7.2 Structured data formats

One of the most common formats is **XML** (Extensible Markup Language), which provides a hierarchical structure to organize and describe data. Lexical resources can be structured in XML files, using elements and attributes to represent words, definitions, translations, and other relevant information.

Another frequently used format is **JSON** (JavaScript Object Notation), a lightweight data interchange format. JSON allows the representation of data in key-value pairs and nested structures, making it ideal for data exchange between different applications and platforms.

Additionally, simple formats like **CSV** (Comma-Separated Values) are used to represent tabular data such as word lists, where each row represents a record and the columns contain the various attributes of the record.

7.3 Markup languages for lexical resources

In the field of lexical resources, specific markup languages are often used to describe and annotate data in a structured manner.

A well-known markup language is XML following the guidelines of the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI)¹⁶, developed specifically for representing and annotating texts in the humanities. TEI provides a comprehensive set of markup elements that allow encoding various aspects of texts, such as structure, language, metadata, and linguistic information. TEI-Lex-0¹⁷ is a specialized extension of TEI focused on encoding lexical resources like dictionaries, thesauri, and glossaries. It offers a set of elements and structures designed specifically for describing lexical data. These elements enable detailed and standardized representation of lexical entries, lemmas, definitions, translations, and other relevant information.

```
<entry>
  <form type="lemma">Apfel</form>
  <sense>
    <def>Edible fruit that comes from apple trees and comes in various varieties and
colors</def>
  </sense>
</entry>
```

Another important markup language is the **Lexical Markup Framework** (LMF), developed specifically for lexical resources such as dictionaries and thesauri. LMF provides a standardized framework for describing lexical data structures, including entries, lemmas, definitions, synonyms, and more.

```
<LexicalEntry>
  <Lemma>Apfel</Lemma>
  <Sense>
    <Definition>Edible fruit that comes from apple trees and comes in various varieties
and colors</Definition>
```

¹⁶ <https://www.tei-c.org/>

¹⁷ <https://dariah-eric.github.io/lexicalresources/pages/TEILex0/TEILex0.html>

```

    </Sense>
    <Language>German</Language>
</LexicalEntry>

```

Additionally, the **TermBase eXchange** (TBX) format is frequently used to represent terminological data such as dictionaries and glossaries. TBX provides a standardized structure for describing terms, definitions, linguistic information, and translations.

```

<termEntry id="1">
  <term>Apfel</term>
  <langSet xml:lang="de">
    <ntig>
      <termNote type="definition">Edible fruit that comes from apple trees and comes in
various varieties and colors</termNote>
    </ntig>
  </langSet>
</termEntry>

```

The **Resource Description Framework** (RDF) offers a flexible way to encode and describe lexical resources by providing a standardized model for representing information and relationships between resources. Using RDF, lexical entries, lemmas, definitions, translations, and other relevant information can be represented as triples, where each triple consists of a subject, a predicate, and an object. This allows complex structures and relationships between lexical resources to be modeled clearly and consistently.

```

@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix onto: <http://example.org/ontology/> .

```

```

<http://example.org/entries/Apfel>
  rdf:type onto:LexicalEntry ;
  onto:hasLemma "Apfel"@de ;
  onto:hasDefinition "Edible fruit that comes from apple trees and comes in various
varieties and colors"@de ;
  onto:inLanguage "German"@de .

```

7.4 Importance of standardized formats for interoperability

Standardized formats play a crucial role in the interoperability of lexical resources by providing a uniform and consistent structure for describing and exchanging data. By using standardized formats such as TEI-Lex-0, LMF, TBX, and RDF, lexical resources can be encoded in a way that facilitates easy exchange between different systems, applications, and platforms. This promotes collaboration and data sharing among researchers, institutions, and projects in the humanities and beyond. Furthermore, standardized formats enable the integration of lexical resources into semantic web applications, knowledge bases, and other digital environments, enhancing their visibility and usability.

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